

Immunotherapeutic potential of Bulgarian intravenous immunoglobulin (Immunovenin-intact 5% IgG)

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Abstract

The scope of this study was to investigate the presence of antibodies against widespread pathogenic viruses, fungi, and bacteria in Bulgarian intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG). A total of 90 batches of Immunovenin-intact 5% IgG (BB-NCIPD EAD Sofia, Bulgaria) and plasma from 64 COVID-19 convalescent donors (CCP) were studied; plasma samples of 32 healthy donors were used as controls. SARS-CoV-2 RBD IgG, IgG antibodies against *Candida albicans*, and IgG antibodies against alpha-hemolysin (Hla) of *Staphylococcus* were determined by semi-quantitative ELISAs. SARS-CoV-2-specific IgG was detected in all “pandemic” batches with a mean (min–max) level of 7.4 ± 3.9 , compared to 4.1 ± 2.4 for CCP. All tested IVIG batches (90/90, 100%) contained IgG antibodies against *Candida albicans* with a mean (min–max) level of 27.4 ± 1.4 , as compared to five positive sera (5/12, 42%) with a level of 17.2 ± 7.6 . A positive result for *S. aureus* anti-Hla IgG was obtained for 88/90 (98%) IVIG batches tested, with a mean (min–max) absorbance of 2.21 (1.5–3.0). The presence of specific IgG antibodies against widespread pathogens in nearly all studied IVIG batches supports their potential use in passive immunization and immunotherapy, pending the development of an algorithm for assessing specific antibody content and subsequent clinical studies.

Keywords

IVIG, immunotherapy, immunoprophylactic

Introduction

Immunoglobulin G (IgG) is one of the most abundant blood proteins, with serum concentrations ranging from 6.6 to 14.5 mg/ml (Beeck and Hellstern 1998). Intravenous immunoglobulins (IVIGs) are therapeutic multispecific IgG derived from the plasma of healthy donors. This blood product was put on the market in the early 1980s as an alternative to intramuscular

immunoglobulins, which were the only treatment available for immunocompromised patients until then. Since the first report in 1981 of increasing platelet count after high-dose IVIg infusion in patients with thrombocytopenia and hypogammaglobulinemia (Wiskott-Aldrich syndrome) (Imbach et al. 1981), the therapeutic benefits of IVIGs have been demonstrated in thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP) and a large number of autoimmune and/or systemic inflammatory diseases, notably Kawasaki

disease, and neurological disorders such as Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS), chronic idiopathic demyelinating polyneuropathy (CIDP), multifocal neuropathy with conduction block (MNCB), and acute myasthenia gravis (Harvey 2005). Immunoglobulin subclass content of IVIGs corresponds to that of normal plasma serum, with a half-life of intact IgG molecules after injection of ~3 weeks (Kaveri et al. 1991). Small concentrations of IgA, IgM, and Fc-dependent IgG aggregates are present in most IVIGs. Because of the large number of donors contributing to one plasma pool for production, the IVIGs represent a broad spectrum of the normal human IgG repertoire, including antibodies to foreign antigens (Kaveri et al. 1991). IVIGs contain antibodies against bacterial, viral, fungal, and parasitic pathogens, depending on the donor's past infections and vaccinations, as well as the endemic nature and frequency of infections (Hartung et al. 2009; Elluru et al. 2015; Wood et al. 2017; Pedraza-Sánchez et al. 2018; Hanson et al. 2019; Donev and Nikolov 2024; Franchini et al. 2024). Therefore, the content and levels of pathogen-specific antibodies differ from batch to batch, which has been demonstrated by measuring neutralizing antibodies against respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) and specific opsonizing antibodies against group B streptococci (GBS) (Fischer et al. 1983; Hemming et al. 1985). Several research studies on IVIG therapy for fungal infections suggest that immunoglobulins play a protective role in infections and inflammation caused by many species of fungi, including *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, *Cryptococcus*, and others (Casadevall and Pirofski 2012; Elluru et al. 2015). The technology for producing Bulgarian IVIG was developed and implemented in 1985. Since then, it has been applied as an effective immunomodulator intravenous product with significant therapeutic potential. However, the multitude of questions about the anti-infectious (viral, fungal, and bacterial) benefits of Bulgarian IVIG remains open and served as an impetus for this study.

The aim of the study is to investigate the presence of antibodies against widespread pathogenic viruses, fungi, and bacteria in Bulgarian intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) to better understand its potential clinical applications.

Materials and methods

Manufacturing process

The manufacturing process for Immunovenin—intact 5% IgG (BB-NCIPD EAD Sofia, Bulgaria)—is outlined in Fig. 1. Plasma for fractionation of 6000 donors goes through the basic cold ethanol fractionation first step, resulting in Fractions II+III, the starting material for the production process described below. Fraction II+III, containing soluble proteins and immunoglobulins, is suspended in solution. The suspension is treated with PEG 6000 for removal of IgM and IgG aggregates using a vibromixer. The resulting precipitate is removed by depth filtration. The filtrate is then cold ethanol fractionated to a final immunoglobulin fraction. The intermediate is further purified by an ion exchange chromatography step, resulting in an IgG-containing solution that is afterwards filtered through a nanofilter (20 nm) for virus reduction. Mannitol (2% v/v) and albumin 20%-BB (sterile solution) at a ratio of 1:5 relative to protein content are added, and after ultrafiltration, the immunoglobulin solution is finally adjusted in terms of pH and sodium chloride content. After depth filtration, the solution goes to sterile filtration and is stored at +37 °C for 28 days for viral inactivation. In the final step, the protein concentration is adjusted to 5%, and the formulation is completed. Prior to storage, the drug substance is sterile filtered and packaged into the final shipping containers.

Materials and study design

For the study, 90 batches of Immunovenin-intact 5% IgG (BB-NCIPD EAD Sofia, Bulgaria) were analyzed. In addition, 64 COVID-19 convalescent plasma (CCP) samples were collected from donors who provided informed consent for plasma donation and study participation at the National Centre of Transfusion Hematology in Sofia, Bulgaria, between January and June 2021. All donors had recently recovered after a laboratory-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection. Severity of COVID-19 was defined according to WHO criteria (WHO 2021). Plasma samples from 32 healthy donors were used as controls.

Figure 1. Overview of the manufacturing process.

Anti-S1 RBD IgG antibodies

Anti-SARS-CoV-2 RBD-specific IgG was determined semi-quantitatively by ELISA (Euroimmun, PerkinElmer Germany Diagnostics GmbH, Germany). According to the manufacturer's instructions, the results were expressed as the absorbance ratio between the test sample and the calibrator ($E_{\text{test}}/E_{\text{calibrator}}$), and values > 1.1 were defined as positive.

Neutralizing anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies

Neutralizing anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibody activity was determined using the 6-plex Human SARS-CoV-2 Variants Neutralizing Antibody Panel and Luminex technology (Invitrogen, Bender MedSystems GmbH, Austria). The assay simultaneously evaluates neutralizing potential against the original wild-type SARS-CoV-2 strain and its five variants (B.1.1.529 (omicron), B.1.617.2 (δ), P.1 (γ), B.1.351 (β), and B.1.1.7 (α)) in a single well. Briefly, the wild-type SARS-CoV-2 S1 and the variant S1 proteins are conjugated to magnetic beads. Samples or controls are added, and SARS-CoV-2-specific antibodies, if present, bind to the conjugated viral proteins. Biotinylated angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), followed by streptavidin–phycoerythrin (PE), are used as detection reagents, which binds to the spike protein on the beads if not blocked by neutralizing antibodies present in the tested samples. The fluorescent signal is negatively proportional to the amount of SARS-CoV-2-specific neutralizing antibodies present in the sample, being maximal in the negative control. The neutralization effect is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Neutralization (\%)} = (1 - (\text{MFI of sample}/\text{MFI of negative control})) \times 100$$

According to the manufacturer's instructions, the cut-off level of the test is 20%.

Immunoglobulin isotypes

For determination of antibody heavy chain subclasses of seven protein targets (IgG1, IgG2, IgG3, IgG4, IgA, IgE, and IgM), the ProcartaPlex Human Antibody Isotyping Panel 7plex and Luminex xMAP technology (Invitrogen, Bender MedSystems GmbH, Austria) were used. Briefly, the Luminex technology is based on a bead array internally dyed with precise proportions of red and infrared fluorophores to create spectrally unique signatures identified by the Luminex xMAP detection systems. Each spectrally unique bead is labeled with antibodies specific for a single heavy chain of the respective subclass/isotype, and the proteins bound are identified with biotinylated antibodies and streptavidin–R-phycoerythrin (RPE). The amount of RPE fluorescence is proportional to the amount of protein present in the sample.

Anti-*Candida albicans* IgG

Anti-*Candida albicans*-specific IgG was determined using a qualitative ELISA (BL International GmbH, Germany). According to the manufacturer's instructions, the results were expressed in units (U). Values above the cutoff were considered positive.

Anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* IgG

For determination of IgG antibodies specific for *S. aureus* alpha-hemolysin (Hla), a homemade ELISA kit was used. The microplate wells (Corning®, USA) were coated with 100 μl of 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ α -hemolysin from *S. aureus* (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) at 37 °C for 1 hour and were blocked with 200 μl of blocking buffer (1% BSA) for another hour at 37 °C. Next, the wells were emptied, filled with 100 μl of IVIG sample (diluted 1:100 in 0.05% sterile PBS), and further incubated for one hour at 37 °C, followed by 3 washing steps with 300 μl of washing buffer (ImmunoChemistry Technologies, USA). The presence of specific IgG was revealed with goat anti-human Fc-specific peroxidase-conjugated IgG (Merck, Germany): 100 μl of conjugate diluted 1:60,000 in 0.05% PBS was added per well and incubated for 30 min at 37 °C, followed by three washing steps with 300 μl washing buffer. Finally, 100 μl of substrate—3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (Sigma-Aldrich, USA)—was added per well and left for 15 minutes at room temperature, followed by 100 μl of stop solution (ImmunoChemistry Technologies, USA) for 5 min before reading (OD 450).

Statistical analysis

All comparisons were performed using GraphPad Prism 6 software (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, CA). An unpaired t-test was used for parametric data, and the Mann–Whitney test for non-parametric data; P values less than 0.05 were considered significant. Correlations were assessed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

Results

The general characteristics of 11 batches produced over a one-year period were first analyzed (Table 1). Overall, the variability observed between the batches was low ($CV \leq 2\%$), indicating a stable and reproducible manufacturing process. Furthermore, the analysis of IgG subclass distribution reproduced the typical values for human plasma (Table 2).

Viral antibodies in IVIG 5%

We analyzed the presence of SARS-CoV-2 RBD-specific IgG antibodies in Immunovenin-intact 5% IgG. The mean level of RBD-specific IgG in 16 batches was 7.4 ± 3.9 , significantly higher than in the CCP group ($n = 64$; 4.1 ± 2.4 , $p = 0.005$) (Fig. 2).

Table 1. Product characteristics and accompanying proteins. General characteristics of 11 batches produced within a one-year period.

Parameter	Unit	Mean	SD (CV%)
Total protein	mg/ml	59.42	1.16 (1.95)
Gamma globulin	%	99.86	0.28 (0.28)
pH		6.91	0.04 (0.57)
Osmolality	mOsmol/kg	445.363	0.94 (0.21)
D-Manitol	mg/ml	20	N/A
Sodium chloride	mg/ml	9	N/A
Albumin	mg/ml	10	N/A
IgA	mg/ml	0.67	0.01 (1.79)

Table 2. Immunoglobulin subclass distribution in IVIG 5%. A total of 80 released batches of the product were analyzed for classes and subclasses of immunoglobulin distribution.

Parameter	Mean (g/L)	Mean (%)	SD
IgG1	12.41083	65.695	7.907
IgG2	3.39919	17.993	2.873
IgG3	1.93028	10.217	0.512
IgG4	0.73347	3.882	2.325
IgA	0.27230	1.441	0.184
IgE	0.00038	0.002	0
IgM	0.14490	0.767	0.058

Figure 2. Levels of anti-SARS-CoV-2 RBD-specific IgG in Immunovenin-intact 5% IVIG and CCP (control group).

In addition, IVIG (n = 16) was analyzed for its neutralizing activity against the S1 protein of six SARS-CoV-2 variants: the wild type, B.1.617.2 (δ), P.1 (γ), B.1.351 (β), B.1.1.529 (omicron), and B.1.1.7 (α). Neutralizing activity was observed for all subtypes in all tested samples. The lowest positive result was detected for the γ variant (Table 3). The mean neutralizing activity ranged from 75.5% for the γ S1 to 91.5% for the α variant. No significant difference was found between IVIG and CCP (n = 64), as the unpaired t-test yielded $p > 0.05$ (Fig. 3).

Anti-*Candida albicans* antibodies in IVIG 5%

Analysis of 90 batches of IVIG 5% for the presence of antibodies against *Candida albicans* showed that all tested samples were positive with a mean level of 27.4 ± 1.4 . For comparison, among 12 randomly selected control sera, 5 were negative and 7 were positive, with a mean level of

Figure 3. Comparison of the neutralizing potential against six SARS-CoV-2 variants between Immunovenin-intact 5% IVIG and CCP. No significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$, unpaired t-test).

Table 3. Neutralizing activity of tested IVIG 5% for SARS-CoV-2 variants. Percentage of neutralization for six SARS-CoV-2 variants.

Target protein	S1 protein	Spike B117	Spike B1351	Spike P1	Spike B16172	Spike B11529
% neutralization (mean)	81.2	91.5	83.8	75.5	80.2	89.7

17.2 ± 7.6 (Fig. 4). A significant difference was observed between IVIG and control group levels ($p < 0.0001$, unpaired t-test).

Figure 4. Comparative analysis of anti-*Candida albicans* IgG levels in Immunovenin-intact 5% IVIG versus control sera. Significantly higher levels were detected in IVIG ($p < 0.0001$, unpaired t-test).

The control group was further analyzed by age. Individuals over 30 years ($n = 4$) showed a mean IgG level of 25.9 ± 1.3 , while those under 30 years ($n = 8$) had a mean of 9.7 ± 4.7 . The unpaired t-test shows a difference ($p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Comparison of anti-*Candida albicans* IgG levels in control group participants aged over 30 years ($n = 4$) versus under 30 years ($n = 8$). A significant difference was observed ($p < 0.0001$, unpaired t-test).

Anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* antibodies in IVIG 5%

All 90 batches from IVIG 5% were analyzed for the presence of IgG against *Staphylococcus aureus* alpha-hemolysin (Hla). As a control group, sera were used from healthy donors 20<30 years old and 20>30 years old. Of the 90 IVIG 5% batches, 88 tested positive for anti-Hla IgG, with a mean level of 2.21 ± 0.36 . In comparison, all control group samples were positive, with a mean level of 1.7 ± 0.37 . The statistical analysis of the unpaired t-test shows a significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 6). When comparing mean anti-Hla IgG levels between the >30 (1.8 ± 0.36) and <30 (1.5 ± 0.30) age groups in the control cohort, no significant difference was observed ($p > 0.05$, unpaired t-test).

Figure 6. Anti-alpha-hemolysin (Hla) IgG levels in Immunovenin-intact 5% IVIG versus the control group. A significant difference was observed ($p < 0.0001$, unpaired t-test).

Discussion

The Bulgarian intravenous immunoglobulin product is a high-quality, well-tolerated source of polyclonal IgG antibodies. It is obtained from a well-established manufacturing process using Bulgarian human plasma for production. In our view, this is an established production process for obtaining a high-yield product from human plasma. Nowadays, human plasma is a highly demanded blood product, which, according to Prevot and Jolles (2020), is expected to be even more sought after in the future. In this study, we investigated the main specifications of the IVIG and the level of potentially treatment-effective antibodies used for different types of infections.

All key physicochemical parameters of the IVIG lots we tested conformed to international standards. Residual IgA was consistently low ($\leq 0.1\%$ of total protein), well below normal serum levels (González-Quintela et al. 2008), and unlikely to pose a clinical risk except in the rare individual ($<1:600$) with anti-IgA antibodies (Sandler et al. 1994; Hammarström et al. 2000). Current evidence does not demonstrate a clear dose-dependence of adverse reactions to trace IgA (Martínez et al. 2021).

According to the findings of Shakib and Stanworth (1980) and French (1986), the concentration level of each immunoglobulin in the serum of healthy individuals depends in part on the number of plasma cells that produce that particular immunoglobulin subclass, the rate of synthesis and catabolism, and the exchange between intra- and extravascular spaces. Their study shows that in adults the concentration of IgG1 (5–12 g/l) is followed by IgG2 (2–6 g/l), IgA1 (0.5–2 g/l), IgM (0.5–1.5 g/l), IgG3 (0.5–1.0 g/l), IgG4 (0.2–1.0 g/l), IgA2 (0–0.2 g/l), IgD (0–0.4 g/l), and IgE (0–0.002 g/l). We found that the concentration and distribution of subclasses and classes of immunoglobulins present in Bulgarian IVIG had the same distribution as the normal level in adult healthy people. We found the highest mean concentration of IgG1 (12.41 g/l), followed by IgG2 (3.39 g/l), IgG3 (1.93 g/l), IgG4 (0.73 g/l), IgA (0.27 g/l), IgM (0.14 g/l), and IgE (0–0.0003 g/l).

Cao et al. (2020) described the effective use of IVIG in COVID-19 in three deteriorating patients. Several studies reported on the benefit of IVIG in critically ill patients in different countries, including the USA, Iran, Italy, China, Turkey, and Bhutan (Lanza et al. 2020; LeVine et al. 2020; Mohtadi et al. 2020; Sakoulas et al. 2020; Zhou et al. 2020; Cao et al. 2021; Esen et al. 2021). We analyzed the presence of RBD-specific IgG in 16 batches of IVIG produced from plasma pools collected during the pandemic period and found a mean ratio of 7.4 ± 3.9 , which is nearly two times higher compared to the mean RBD-specific IgG ratio (4.1 ± 2.4) of donors' convalescent plasma. Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG), derived from a pool of at least a thousand healthy donors, contains natural IgG antibodies against various antigens at various thresholds of detection owing to the accumulation of low antibody concentrations from single individuals.

Importantly, neutralization assays demonstrated significant in vitro activity against wild-type SARS-CoV-2 and all major variants of concern (α , β , γ , δ , and Omicron), with neutralization levels ranging from 75.5% to 91.5% and no significant difference compared to convalescent plasma ($p > 0.05$). These findings are consistent with reports from other regions showing robust anti-RBD and neutralizing antibodies in IVIG post-2021 production (Cao et al. 2020; Mohtadi et al. 2020; Jordan et al. 2022). IVIG may be a potent source of passive and neutralizing immunotherapy agents for patients in low-resource settings.

Research studies (Reid et al. 1997; Kohler et al. 2003; Stäger et al. 2003; Kozel et al. 2004) found that natural antibodies play an important role in protection against fungal pathogens, including *Candida* infections. *Candida albicans* is a common member of the microflora in humans on mucosal surfaces until the host becomes immunodeficient or the balance is disrupted and candidiasis devel-

ops. So even in the absence of infection, humans tend to develop anti-*Candida albicans* antibodies, including IgG.

All tested IVIG lots exhibited high titers of *Candida albicans*-specific IgG (27.4 ± 1.4), significantly exceeding levels in healthy donor sera (17.2 ± 7.6). Age-stratified analysis of controls showed higher anti-*Candida* IgG in donors ≥ 30 years (25.9 ± 1.3) vs. <30 years (9.7 ± 4.7), reflecting cumulative mucosal antigen exposure. Similar results have been reported for other commercial IVIG preparations (Wang et al. 2023).

In this study, we show that antigen-specific IgG anti-*Candida albicans* antibodies were detected among all tested IVIGs from pooled plasma from healthy donors, with high levels of specific IgG in different IVIG lots.

Many *Staphylococcus aureus* strains produce alpha-hemolysin (Hla) (Harshman 1979; Gray and Kehoe 1984), a proteinaceous cytolysin that damages cells by forming hydrophilic pores across the plasma membrane (Tobkes et al. 1985; Watanabe et al. 1987). There is agreement on the pathogenicity of this toxin in mammals (O'Reilly et al. 1986), but in humans, the pathogenicity has been questioned because human cells have been found to be unresponsive to this type of toxin. (McCartney and Arbuthnott 1978). Moreover, the toxin has been recognized as the cause of skin necrosis and lethal infection, as well as neurotoxic action, both in humans and animals by exerting cytotoxic effects on several types of cells (Berube and Wandenburg 2013). IVIG therapy could possibly be helpful in the treatment of this type of infection. A broad spectrum of specific IgG can neutralize the effects of Hla and have a beneficial outcome. We analyzed the presence of anti-Hla IgG and found that all except 2 of the tested 90 batches of IVIG had high levels of specific antibodies (2.21 ± 0.36 mean) compared to the control group (1.7 ± 0.37 mean). According to the findings of Bhakdi et al. (1989), the hyperimmune globulin preparations with high-titer anti-alpha-toxin antibodies effectively protect against the cytotoxic effects of alpha-toxin. We also found a high level of anti-Hla IgG in the IVIG that, with further characterization of functional antibodies, can evaluate the potential of clinical use of IVIG for patients with *Staphylococcus aureus* infection.

Using titer measurements against common pathogens and functional cell-based in vitro assays, we demonstrated full functionality in epitope binding of the IgG antibodies in Bulgarian IVIG. These data suggest that this product provides functional antibodies at protective levels to patients. Thus, Bulgarian IVIG is fully functional and has the potential to expand its use in clinical practice. The prophylactic or therapeutic benefits of IVIG in this context were initially to expand the view of IVIG treatment in delivering specific antibodies to recipients who are unable to produce them, particularly collective antibodies that protect against different infections.

The limitations of the study

The study is limited to in vitro immunological assessments. While antibody levels and neutralization capacity were demonstrated, no clinical trials or patient-based

studies were conducted to confirm therapeutic or prophylactic efficacy in real-world settings. While quantitative antibody data are presented, the study does not define clinically protective thresholds for the antibodies measured, limiting interpretation of their potential efficacy in disease prevention or treatment.

Conclusion

The antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties of Bulgarian IVIG make this intravenous immunotherapeutic product essential for immune prophylaxis and effective in immunotherapy applications when options or specific treatments for infections are limited. A high level of homogenous antibodies from people who originate from the same geographic place makes IVIG a product with rich collective antibodies.

Experience with IVIG therapy in fungal, bacterial, and viral infections is still limited, but evidence suggests that immunoglobulin plays a protective role against infection and inflammation. It is difficult for clinicians to establish an anti-infection IVIG protocol due to the lack of quantity standards and consistent data. The efficacy of IVIG therapy can be beneficial by analyzing the antibodies and the protective capacity against pathogens causing the infection. These findings manifest interest in IVIG regarding a broad spectrum of beneficial use in clinical practice, and further characterization of functional antibodies will be important, given the possibility of expanding the clinical use of IVIG for severe infections.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, V.D., G.N., M.N.; methodology, V.D., G.N., M.N.; formal and statistical analysis, Y.T., R.E.; J.N.;T.S.; data curation, M.N.; writing—original draft preparation, V.D.; visualization, V.D.; supervision, M.N.; project administration, G.N.; funding acquisition, V.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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